

Farm machinery

Manual rice transplanter use in Burma

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More than 3.5 million ha of the 4.8 million ha rice in Burma is transplanted. Transplanting traditionally is women's responsibility. The Agricultural Mechanization Department (AMD) and Agricultural Corporation (AC) reproduced 30 IRRI developed manually operated mechanical transplanters for field testing in 1979.

AMD made 10 modifications: replaced the operating handle with a better grip, changed to a free-hanging counter weight cam for better retraction of pickers, replaced the ratchet with an over-running clutch and the chain roller with a star wheel for better movement, changed the buckle for planting depth to a hook with screw and nut for easier fabrication, added a reinforcing bar and a coil spring between frame members for durability, inserted an inverted U-shaped holder in the pickers to improve hold, added an adjusting screw at the stop block to adjust picking angle, added a seedling guard plate to prevent the seed mat from deforming, put in a reinforcement bracket for each pivot pin for durability, and eliminated the flat carriage bar for better movement of the tray. Bamboo is used instead of wood in seedbed preparation to reduce costs.

The modified transplanter reduces transplanting costs 40%. Hand transplanting costs US\$26.79, the manual transplanter US\$17.66. (These estimates depend on the wage rate of an area, the cost of the transplanter, and its transplanting capacity. Soil type, level of land preparation, water depth, and operator skill also alter estimates.)

The government introduced the manual rice transplanter with dynamic demonstrations, but farmer adoption has been low (see table). Five problems merit consideration:

1. The rice area has not increased

Yearly manufacture and uses of manually operated mechanical transplanter in Burma.

Year	Manufacturer ^a	Number produced	Number in fields	Transplanted area (ha)
1980	AMD	300		
1981	AMD	1000		
1982	AMD	1000	750	4608
1983	HIC	1000	1000	4219
1984	HIC	500	697	1624
1985	HIC	100	1400	8097

^a HIC = Heavy Industries Corporation.

2. A well-organized program to train farmers to operate the transplanter is important.
3. Existing institutions and infrastructure need to be improved to provide repair and replacement facilities within easy reach of

farmers.

4. Target areas for adoption should have the right soil type, proper drainage capabilities, sufficient institutional and infrastructure support, and enough motivated farmers.
5. A well-organized research and development program is needed to solve specific problems in specific areas. □

Farming systems

Pigeonpea genotypes and rice yield in an intercropping system

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We tested different pigeonpea genotypes in an intercropping system with rice

during the 1986-87 wet season. Soil was laterite and sandy loam with pH 5.2, 0.37% total N, 16 kg available P/ha, and 160 kg available K/ha.

Nine pigeonpea genotypes were grown in paired rows of 30/90 cm alone and intercropped with Subhadra rice (90 d duration). Five rows of rice were planted in the interspace of pigeonpea. The intercrops received 30-18-25 kg NPK/ha, rice alone 60-18-25 kg NPK/ha, and pigeonpea alone 20-18-17 kg NPK/ha.

Pigeonpea genotypes differed in their effect on rice yield (see table). The

Yields of pigeonpea genotypes intercropped with rice. Bhubaneswar, Orissa, India, 1986-87 wet season.

Genotype	Intercropped rice yield (t/ha)	Pigeonpea yield (t/ha)		Land equivalent ratio
		Alone	Intercropped	
Pigeonpea				
ICPL 138	1.7	0.6	0.2	1.16
ICPL 227	1.2	0.8	0.7	1.37
ICPL 265	1.2	0.6	0.5	1.40
ICPL 270	1.2	0.5	0.3	1.09
ICPL 295	1.3	0.4	0.4	1.56
ICPL 186	1.0	0.5	0.2	0.81
DAS83-1	1.1	0.8	0.3	0.88
DAS83-2	1.2	0.9	0.4	1.03
R60	1.1	1.2	0.9	1.24
Rice alone				
Subhadra	2.2			
LSD (0.05)	0.3	0.1	0.1	0.21

highest rice yield (1.7 t/ha) was with ICPL 138; the lowest with ICPL 186 (1.0 t/ha). Rice yields from the intercrop were 22-57% less than yields of rice alone.

Pigeonpea yields in the intercropped plots were 2-62% less than in the monocrop. The most compatible rice - pigeonpea combination featured ICPL 295 (56% yield advantage). □

Rice-based cropping systems for optimum production under resource constraints

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During 1979-81, rice variety Jajati (135 d duration) was grown during the wet season with 80-18-33 kg NPK/ha.

Wheat variety Sonalika (95 d duration), mungbean variety Sujata (70 d), and peanut variety AK12-24 (120 d) were grown after rice in the dry season at 3 moisture regimes (1, 3, and 5 irrigations to wheat; 1, 2, and 3 irrigations to mungbean; 1, 3, and 4 irrigations to peanut). Three fertility levels (level 1 = 120-26-50 kg NPK/ha for wheat; 20-18-33 kg NPK/ha for mungbean and peanut; level 2 = 2/3 of level 1; level 3 = 1/3 of level 1) were tested in a split-plot design with three replications.

Rice was transplanted at 15- × 10-cm spacing; wheat and mungbean were sown at 20 × 5 cm; peanut was sown at 30 × 10 cm. The soil was an acidic Latosol, sandy loam texture, with pH 5.9, EC 0.233 dS/m, 0.457% organic C, 0.04% total N, 66.6 kg available P/ha, and 300 kg available K/ha.

Rice yield was low in 1980 because of gall midge attack. Mean total yield was highest from rice - peanut (4.3 t/ha) followed by rice - wheat (3.0 t/ha) (Table 1). Rice - peanut also yielded more protein, carbohydrate, and energy.

Yields of wheat and peanut increased with increasing irrigation; mungbean yields decreased after two irrigations. As

Table 1. Efficiency of cropping system under limited irrigation and fertilizer supply.^a Bhubaneswar, India, 1979-81.

Cropping system	Yield (t/ha)				Protein ^b (t/ha)	Carbohydrate (t/ha)	Energy (MJ × 10 ³ /ha)
	1979	1980	1981	Mean			
Rice - wheat	3.1 (1.1)	1.1 (1.0)	1.9 (0.8)	2.0 (1.0)	0.2	1.7	33.4
Rice - mungbean	3.1 (0.4)	1.2 (0.5)	2.0 (0.5)	2.1 (0.5)	0.2	1.4	27.1
Rice - peanut	3.1 (2.2)	1.2 (1.8)	2.3 (2.3)	2.2 (2.1)	0.5	1.6	57.4

^a Figures in parentheses indicate the dry season crop yield. ^b Protein, carbohydrate, and energy calculated for edible portions only as per standards fixed by the National Institute of Nutrition (ICMR), Hyderabad, India.

Table 2. Effect of irrigation and fertility level (F1, 2, 3) on grain yield of wheat, mungbean, and peanut grown after rice.^a Bhubaneswar, India, 1979-81.

Number of irrigation	Grain yield (t/ha)				
	F1	F2	F3	Mean	
	Wheat				
1 (I1)	1.03	0.80	0.64	0.82	
3 (I2)	1.32	1.09	0.63	1.01	
5 (I3)	1.31	1.06	0.84	1.07	
Mean	1.22	0.98	0.70	0.97	
	Mungbean				
1 (I1)	0.36	0.43	0.41	0.40	
2 (I2)	0.66	0.46	0.42	0.51	
3 (I3)	0.55	0.46	0.35	0.45	
Mean	0.52	0.45	0.39	0.45	
	Peanut				
1 (I1)	1.95	1.75	1.40	1.70	
3 (I2)	2.64	2.33	1.78	2.25	
4 (I3)	2.60	2.51	2.12	2.41	
Mean	2.40	2.20	1.17	2.12	
LSD (0.05)	Wheat		Mungbean		Peanut
I	0.10		0.04		0.05
F	0.04		0.03		0.04
F×I	0.09		0.05		0.08
I×F	0.12		0.06		0.08
CV (%)	Wheat		Mungbean		Peanut
I	10		10		3
F	7		9		3

^aF×I = LSD of 2 submeans at the same level of main. I×F = LSD of 2 main means at same level of different levels of sub. CV (%) I = CV of main plot, F = CV of subplots.

fertility level decreased yield of all crops was reduced.

The interactions were significant at all

levels of irrigation and fertility (Table 2). The best responses were with mid-level irrigation and high fertility. □

ERRATA

IRRN 12:5 (Oct 1987) Performance of improved rice varieties in farmers' fields in Bhutan, by N. Q. R. Nathaniels, et al. In the table (p. 5), the site mean yield for

Techuzamba, Wangdiphodrang, should read 6.7 t/ha (not 3.3 t/ha).

IRRN 125 (Oct 1987) p. 37. Chemical analyses and thermal studies of azolla. The first author's name should read M. L. Aldema. □